

Mixed Ligand Complexes of Cu(II) and Ni(II) with Tertiary Amines and Aromatic Aldehyde or Ketone

RAKESH KUMAR KOHLI and P. K. BHATTACHARYA

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, M.S. University, Baroda-300 002

Manuscript received 27 January 1976, revised 18 September 1976, accepted 10 November 1976

Mixed ligand complexes of type $[M.A.N-N]ClO_4$, where $M = Cu(II)$ or $Ni(II)$; $N-N =$ bipyridyl or *o*-phenanthroline, and $A =$ salicylaldehyde, 2-OH-1-naphthaldehyde or 2-OH-acetophenone have been prepared. Reactions of these compounds have been carried out with ammonia, which lead to the formation of Schiff base complexes of salicylaldehyde, 2-OH-1-naphthaldehyde or 2-OH-acetophenone.

The compounds have been characterized by elemental analyses, spectral, magnetic and conductance studies.

STUDY of mixed ligand complexes containing dipyriddy and *o*-phenanthroline has invited the attention of many workers. Dutta and co-workers¹ reported the synthesis of variety of *α*-oxovanadium(IV) heterochelates containing bipyridyl and *o*-phenanthrolines. Chidambaram and Bhattacharya isolated heterochelates of Cu(II) containing dipyriddy and amino acids^{2,3}. Mixed ligand complexes of Zn(II) containing mercapto acids as secondary ligands and dipyriddy as a primary ligand have also been reported⁴. Mixed ligand complexes of 2,3-dihydroxy naphthalene and dipyriddy or *o*-phenanthroline have been studied with a series of oxocations⁵. In the present investigation attempts have been made to isolate the complexes of the type $[M.A.(N-N)]ClO_4$ where $A =$ salicylaldehyde, 2-OH-1-naphthaldehyde or 2-OH-acetophenone and $N-N =$ dipyriddy or *o*-phenanthroline and $M = Cu(II)$ or $Ni(II)$. The mixed ligand complexes have been treated with ammonia.

Experimental

Ligands used were of AR quality. The metal salts used were copper acetate and nickel chloride of AR grade.

$[Sal.(Dipy/o-phen)Cu(II)]ClO_4$

The above complex was prepared by taking equimolar ratio of metal-acetate and the two ligands. To 0.5M solution of Copper acetate in water, equimolar quantity of solid dipyriddy (or *o*-phenanthroline) was added and the mixture was stirred to get a blue coloured solution. This was followed by the addition of equimolar alcoholic solution of salicylaldehyde or (2-OH-1-naphthaldehyde or 2-OH-acetophenone). This reaction mixture was stirred and then dilute solution of $NaClO_4$ was added until the precipitation was complete. It was then refluxed on water bath for half an hour. The isolated solids were filtered, washed first with alcohol to remove unreacted

dipyriddy or (*o*-phenanthroline) and then with water. They were dried and analysed. The compounds have a low solubility in water and organic solvents and hence could not be recrystallised.

Preparation of Schiff base complex :

These complexes were prepared by two methods : (i) The preformed mixed complexes (I) were treated with excess of ammonia (~50 ml) in alcoholic medium (~30 ml) and warmed on a water bath for about an hour with intermittent stirring. The solid obtained was washed with hot water and alcohol, dried and analysed. They had varying colours from light green to bottle green. (ii) To the metal chloride solution an excess of ammonia was added till the hydroxide formed got dissolved giving metal amine complex. To this was added an equimolar alcoholic solution of dipyriddy and salicylaldehyde, followed by the addition of sodium perchlorate solution until the precipitation was complete. The reaction mixture was refluxed for about half an hour, to ensure the completion of Schiff base complex formation. It was then filtered, washed with water and alcohol, dried and analysed.

All the compounds are found to be crystalline, stable in atmosphere and sparingly soluble in water and organic solvents.

The compounds were analysed for metal and N contents. TLC analysis shows them to be free from impurities. Magnetic measurements were done at room temperature using Guoy balance. Conductivity measurement was carried out in water using Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge, Type CLO/01A. Visible spectra of the complexes were obtained in chloroform and acetone on DU2 Beckman Spectrophotometer, in the range 300-1000 nm. IR spectra was recorded in nujol in the range 4000-625 cm^{-1} on a Perkin Elmer Model 427, spectrophotometer.

The analytical data have been presented in table 1.

KHOLI & BHATTACHARYA : MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF CU(II) AND NI(II) ETC.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA; ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA AND MAGNETIC MOMENT VALUES OF MIXED-LIGAND AND MIXED IMINE SCHIFF BASE COMPLEXES OF CU(II) AND NI(II)

No.	Name of the complex	Metal %		Nitrogen %		max	B.M.	Conductance mhos.cm ⁻¹	
		Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found				
1.	(Sal.dipy.Cu(II))ClO ₄	14.46	13.89	6.37	6.25	490 540 620	73	2.03	123
2.	(Salimin.dipy.(Cu(II))ClO ₄	14.49	14.04	9.58	9.69	400 530 600	89	1.93	100
3.	(2-OH-Acph.dipy.(Cu(II))ClO ₄	13.98	13.88	6.16	5.93	470 500 520	77	1.86	102
4.	(2-OH-Acphimin.dipy.Cu(II))ClO ₄	14.01	13.78	9.26	8.83	480 510 530	78	1.87	conducting
5.	(2-OH-1-naphthal.dipy.Cu(II))ClO ₄	13.01	12.79	5.73	6.13	485 510 550	63	1.79	80
6.	(2-OH-1-naphthalimin.dipy.Cu(II))ClO ₄	12.96	12.68	8.58	8.99	460 490 510	73	1.83	conducting
7.	(Sal.o-phen.Cu(II))ClO ₄	13.20	12.90	5.81	5.74	480 520 570	75	1.75	conducting
8.	(Salimin.o-phen.Cu(II))ClO ₄	13.17	12.98	8.70	9.19	480 540 590	86	1.81	conducting
9.	(2-OH-Acph.-o-phen.Cu(II))ClO ₄	12.75	12.49	5.61	5.53	510 530	81	1.80	conducting
10.	(2-OH-Acphimin.o-phen.Cu(II))ClO ₄	12.80	12.58	8.46	8.71	500 530 570	86	1.92	conducting
11.	(2-OH-1-naphthal. o-phen.Cu(II))ClO ₄	11.93	11.68	5.26	5.53	500 520 570	82	1.78	77
12.	(2-OH-1-naphthalimin.o-phen.Cu(II))ClO ₄	11.98	11.74	7.92	8.19	520 580	77	1.81	conducting
13.	(Salimin.dipy.Ni(II))ClO ₄	13.55	13.72	9.69	9.12	470 570	55	1.30*	conducting
14.	(Salimin. o-phen.Ni(II))ClO ₄	12.32	12.19	8.81	9.60	520 570	58	1.34*	80
15.	(2-OH-Acphimin.dipy.Ni(II))ClO ₄	13.06	12.88	9.34	10.09	520 550	70	1.53*	conducting
16.	(2-OH-Acphimin. o-phen.Ni(II))ClO ₄	11.94	11.64	8.54	9.20	490 sh 520 540	146	1.56*	86
17.	(2-OH-1-naphthalimin.dipy.Ni(II))ClO ₄	12.12	12.01	8.67	8.77	550 sh 570 530	158	1.53*	conducting
18.	(2-OH-1-naphthalimin. o-phen.Ni(II))ClO ₄	11.17	11.01	7.99	8.26	520 540	192	1.41*	conducting

*Partially paramagnetic.

 Where Sal. = Salicylaldehydato; Salimin. = Salicylaldiminato; 2-OH-Acph. = 2-OH-Acetophenonato;
 2-OH-Acphimin. = 2-OH-Acetophenoniminato; 2-OH-1-naphthal. = 2-OH-1-naphthaldehydato;
 2-OH-1-naphthalimin. = 2-OH-1-naphthalaldiminato.

Results and Discussion

The molar conductance of the complexes show them to be 1 : 1 electrolytic in nature, indicating the presence of ClO_4^- in the outer sphere.

The analyses of the compounds correspond to the expected mixed ligand complexes. The reaction of the metal ion with the two ligands has been shown in scheme A. On treating the mixed ligand complexes with ammonia, salicylaldehyde or 2-OH-1-naphthaldehyde or 2-OH-acetophenone the Schiff base complexes are formed as shown in scheme B. The compound (II) could also be obtained by treating the metal ammonia complex with one equivalent of salicylaldehyde or (other primary ligand) and another of equimolar bipyridyl or *o*-phenanthroline followed by the addition of dilute solution of NaClO_4 as shown in scheme C.

complexes show a broad band at ~ 590 nm indicating square planar geometry. The Cu(II) imine Schiff base complexes show a band at ~ 550 nm ($\epsilon = 80$). The displacement of the band to the lower wavelength in Schiff base complexes indicates formation of stronger M-N bond⁶.

The Ni(II) complexes exhibit some paramagnetism. Partial paramagnetism in Ni(II) Schiff base complexes have been studied and interpreted in detail earlier^{7,8}. This has been attributed to partial polymerisation due to oxygen-bridging. Similar considerations can explain the partial paramagnetism in the above complexes.

The visible spectra of Ni(II) complexes show a band at ~ 550 nm. There are no bands beyond 600 nm confirming square planar geometry for the

In the case of Ni(II), compounds corresponding to (I) could not be obtained. However, compound(II) where M is Ni(II), could be prepared by the second method, treating the $[\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_3)_4]^{2+}$ complex with equimolar solution of A and N-N and adding to this dilute solution of NaClO_4 , until the precipitation was complete.

All the Cu(II) complexes are paramagnetic. Magnetic moment values correspond to the presence of one unpaired electron. The spectra of type (I)

complexes in solution. This can be attributed to the breaking of polymerisation in solution.

In the IR spectra of all the complexes, band in the region 3400 cm^{-1} is absent, indicating that the O-H hydrogen of the aldehyde or the Schiff base gets dissociated after complexation. In the copper complex (I) a band is observed at 1625 cm^{-1} corresponding to C=O stretching. In the spectra of Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes (II), a band at 1600 cm^{-1} corresponding to C=N stretching appears. The shift

of the C=O band in Cu(II) complexes on reaction with ammonia, indicates Schiff base formation. There is a strong band at 3200 cm^{-1} corresponding to N-H stretching frequency.

The IR spectra of all the complexes show a strong band at 1100 cm^{-1} , corresponding to asymmetric stretching in ClO_4^- . The band at 900 cm^{-1} corresponding to symmetric stretch is absent. This shows that ClO_4^- ion has Td symmetry and is ionic in nature. If there were coordinated ClO_4^- the symmetry will be reduced to C_{3v} and symmetric stretching vibration occurring at 900 cm^{-1} would have been observed.

Acknowledgement

Authors thanks are due to Prof. S. M. Sethna, the then Head, Department of Chemistry, M. S. University of Baroda, for providing all the laboratory facilities. We are also thankful to Multi-Chem. Research Centre, Nandesari for the generous recording

of the IR spectra of complexes. One of the authors (R.K.K.) is also thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi for awarding the Junior Research Fellowship.

References

1. R. L. DUTTA and S. GHOSH, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 247.
2. M. V. CHIDAMBARAM and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Inst. Chem. (India)*, 1972, **44**, 144.
3. M. V. CHIDAMBARAM, "Formation and Stability of Some Amino Acid Chelates", Ph.D. Thesis, M.S. Univ., Baroda, 1972, p. 234.
4. B. R. PANGHAL and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **4**, 394.
5. A. T. OHERAPAKILA and J. B. STATER, *Vses Zaochem. Politekn. Inst.*, 1964, **32**, 105.
6. H. S. FRENCH, M. Z. MAGGE and E. SHEFFIELD, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 1924.
7. R. H. HOLM and J. M. O'CONNOR, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1971, **14**, 252.
8. L. SACCONI, *Transitional Metal Chemistry*, 1968, **4**, 269.
9. R. H. BALUNGI and A. CHAKRAVORTY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, **12**, 981.